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ABSTRACTS

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Application of Machine Learning methods to predict Protein Structure

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Abstract: Proteins play a fundamental role in various biological processes, and their three-dimensional (3D) structure is critical for understanding their functions. However, determining protein structures experimentally can be challenging and time-consuming. Machine learning (ML) has emerged as a powerful tool for predicting and understanding protein geometry based on sequence information. Through the years, a diverse set of both supervised and unsupervised machine learning techniques have been employed to address these challenges, making substantial contributions to the advancement of protein structure prediction methodologies. In this study, we explore the application of ML techniques to analyse and interpret protein geometry. In our study we have developed regression-based Machine Learning models to unravel the complex relationships between protein sequence and geometry. The machine learning model have been able to identify the dimers of 3D protein structures. Our Machine Learning study has the potential to revolutionize drug discovery, protein engineering, and our understanding of biological systems.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Protein geometry, Regression model, Machine Learning

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